

ISic0650

I.Sicily inscription 0650

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

S. Lucia in Achradina

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 6458

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 14 cm

Width 15.5 cm

Depth 1.2 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 4: 25 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. κάθθανα γηραλέ[ος---][ένι]
2. αὐτῶς φήμη ἴγαῦρ[ος][---]
3. ἀμεμφής · εἶναι [δ' εὐχόμενος][---]
4. γείνομαί ἅπαντω[---]

Apparatus

Text of Manganaro 1994 controlled against photograph

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644890

PHI 332970

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 44.0793
1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 44.0738.12
undefined, undefined 1888-. Bulletin épigraphique. *Bulletin épigraphique*. At 1995.0029
undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.
Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 397
Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité*. 106: 79-118. At 97-98 no.12 fig.17

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